

Supplementary file 2. Quality assessment of included studies

Reference	Quality Assessment Criteria Probing Questions (Q)									Study level quality score		Quality
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Total No Yes (Y)	Percentage of Yes (Y) %	
Asiegbu, Lebelo & Tabit, 2020 [63]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	U	7	77.7	Moderate
Barreira et al., 2024 [64]	Y	Y	U	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	High
Bhowmik et al., 2022 [65]	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	U	U	6	66.6	Moderate
Budiarso et al., 2021 [66]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	U	7	77.7	Moderate
da Silva Oliveira et al., 2021 [67]	Y	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	U	Y	6	66.6	Moderate
Das et al., 2021 [68]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	U	7	77.7	High
Elexson et al., 2017 [69]	Y	Y	U	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	Moderate
Fayemi et al., 2021 [70]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	9	100	High
Jenifer & Sathiyamurthy, 2020 [71]	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	U	U	6	66.6	Moderate
Johura et al., 2020 [72]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	9	100	High

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Khalil & Gomaa, 2016 [73]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	9	100	High
Latchumaya et al., 2021 [74]	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	Moderate
Mora-Coto et al., 2025 [75]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	9	100	High
Novira et al., 2020 [76]	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	U	6	66.6	Moderate
Plessis et al., 2017 [77]	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	High
Ritcher et al., 2021 [78]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	9	100	High
Salazar-Llorente et al., 2021 [79]	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	High
Sánchez et al., 2021 [80]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	U	7	77.7	High
Sivakumar et al., 2021 [81]	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	High
Tabassum, Saha & Islam, 2015 [82]	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	U	U	6	66.6	Moderate

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	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Total No Yes (Y)	Percentage of Yes (Y) %	
Taha et al., 2023 [83]	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	High
Yaici et al., 2017 [84]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	9	100	High
Zurita et al., 2020 [85]	Y	Y	U	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.7	Moderate

Q1: Was the sample frame appropriate to address the target population?

Q2: Were study participants sampled in an appropriate way?

Q3: Was the sample size adequate?

Q4: Were the study subjects and the setting described in detail?

Q5: Was the data analysis conducted with sufficient coverage of the identified sample?

Q6: Were valid methods used for the identification of the condition?

Q7: Was the condition measured in a standard, reliable way for all participants?

Q8: Was there appropriate statistical analysis?

Q9: Was the response rate adequate, and if not, was the low response rate managed appropriately?